

Adsorption of Phenol from Solution in Benzene by Carbon Blacks as Influenced by Surface Oxides

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Adsorption of phenol from its solution in benzene has been studied by three carbon blacks which were used before as well as after evacuation at 600° and 1000°. The results show that phenol is preferred to benzene by each carbon. The isotherms are V-shaped and are of type II of the Schay and Nagy classification. The preference of the surface for phenol increases in the presence of surface oxides to such an extent as to bring about perpendicular orientation of the phenol molecules so that the -OH groups lie closer to the oxygen containing sites at the carbons surface. The perpendicular orientation changes gradually to parallel orientation with the increasing elimination of the surface oxides on evacuation.

THE influence of surface oxides on adsorption of phenols from aqueous phase by carbons which is of special significance in view of their presence in waste waters from plants used for thermal processing of coal and manufacture of a variety of industrial products has engaged the attention of several investigators in recent years¹⁻⁴. The observations, however, have not always been in conformity with one another. Thus while the work of Graham⁵ as well as that of Coughlin, Ezra and Tan¹ shows that the adsorption is suppressed that of Epstein, Malle and Mattson⁶ suggests that it is enhanced and that of Clauss, Boehm and Hofmann⁴ indicates that it is not affected by the presence of surface oxides. The previous work reported from these laboratories⁶ showed that at low concentrations the surface oxide that is acidic and comes off as carbon dioxide (acidic CO₂-complex) lowers while that which comes off as carbon monoxide (CO-complex) enhances the adsorption of phenol. Since phenol and water are both polar and are capable of having specific interactions with the polar sites on carbon surface, it may be preferable to study adsorption from a non-aqueous solvent like benzene. The present work was, therefore, undertaken.

Experimental

Materials: Three carbon blacks, namely Spheron-C, Spheron-6 and Mogul were used before as well as after evacuation at 600° and 1000°. The specific surface areas (nitrogen, B. E. T.) and oxygen contents are given in Table 1. Phenol and benzene used were of A. R. (B. D. H.) quality.

Procedure: Several 0.5 g portions of each carbon (oven-dried at 120°) were mixed with about 5g (accurately weighed) of phenol solutions in benzene of different concentrations in 20 ml glass tubes with narrow necks which were then sealed. The contents were shaken mechanically for 24 hr by placing the tubes in a revolving wheel making 12 rev/min and

held in a thermostat (25±0.1°). The tubes were then allowed to stand as such at the same temperature for the next 24 hr to allow the particles to settle down. The fall in concentration was then determined by examining a small portion of the clear supernatant liquid interferometrically, using Carl Zeiss laboratory Model LI-3.

Results and Discussion

The isotherms of concentration change (also termed as composite adsorption isotherms) due to adsorption of phenol and benzene at 25° by the various carbon blacks from mixtures of different concentrations are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. The

amount of adsorption, expressed as $\frac{W_0 \Delta C}{m}$ (where

W_0 is the total weight of the mixture added to mg of the adsorbent and ΔC is the change in weight

Fig. 1. Composite isotherms of adsorption from phenol benzene mixtures on original and outgassed samples of Spheron-C.

Fig. 2. Composite isotherms of adsorption from phenol benzene mixtures on original and outgassed samples of Spheron-6.

Fig. 3. Composite isotherms of adsorption from phenol benzene mixtures on original and outgassed samples of Mogul.

fraction produced as a result of adsorption) and normalised with respect to unit surface, has been plotted along the ordinate while the equilibrium concentration, expressed as weight fraction of phenol, has been plotted along the abscissa as is usual in treatment of adsorption from binary mixtures governed by the general equation

$$\frac{W_0 \Delta C}{m} = W_1^g (1 - C) - W_2^g C$$

where W_1^g and W_2^g are the weights of phenol and benzene adsorbed per g adsorbent when the weight fraction of phenol in solution at equilibrium is C .

Each isotherm indicates preference of the surface for phenol. The isotherms are V-shaped, approach a certain maximum value and then fall linearly downward. In such cases, according to Schay and Nagy's treatment^{7,8}, used by various workers⁸⁻¹⁰,

the extrapolation of the linear section to $C=0$ (as shown by the dotted lines in the figures) gives an intercept at the ordinate which corresponds to the weight of phenol alone in the adsorbed phase,

for then $\frac{W_0 \Delta C}{m} = W_1^g$. This amount has been

taken by these workers to completely cover the surface of 1 g of the adsorbent by a unimolecular layer. Since in the present case, adsorption has been plotted on the basis of 1 m^2 of surface, the intercept should be 0.30 mg or 0.62 mg depending upon parallel or perpendicular orientation of the molecules on the surface. The molecular areas of phenol are taken as $52 \text{ \AA}$ and $25 \text{ \AA}^2$ in the two respective orientations¹¹. Considering the isotherms for the original carbon blacks, the actual values are seen to be 0.56, 0.58, 0.60 mg (cf. Table 1) in

TABLE 1—OXYGEN CONTENTS, SPECIFIC SURFACE AREAS (B.E.T. N_2) AND THE AMOUNTS OF PHENOL ADSORBED AS OBTAINED FROM EXTRAPOLATION OF THE LINEAR SECTION OF EACH ISOTHERM TO ZERO CONCENTRATION IN THE CASE OF VARIOUS CARBONS

Sample	Oxygen Content (g/100 g)	Surface area (B.E.T. N_2) (m^2/g)	Amount of phenol adsorption as obtained from the extrapolation of linear section to zero concentration (mg/m^2)
Spheron-C (Original)	3.1	254	0.56
Spheron-C (600°-outgassed)	1.2	320	0.42
Spheron-C (1000°-outgassed)	0.6	231	0.35
Spheron-6 (Original)	3.1	120	0.58
Spheron-6 (600°-outgassed)	1.3	115	0.48
Spheron-6 (1000°-outgassed)	0.6	100	0.39
Mogul (Original)	7.8	308	0.60
Mogul (600°-outgassed)	1.7	335	0.49
Mogul (1000°-outgassed)	0.65	328	0.31

the case of Spheron-C, Spheron-6 and Mogul, respectively. This shows that phenol molecules acquire perpendicular orientation when adsorbed on oxygen-populated surfaces from solution in benzene instead of parallel orientation. The perpendicular orientation evidently permits accommodation of maximum number of phenol molecules on the surface; such an orientation is also conducive to hydrogen bonding as $-\text{OH}$ groups of phenol then lie closer to oxygen sites on the surface.

But as the carbon blacks are outgassed, first at 600° and then at 1000° , the extent of adsorption is seen to undergo a progressive fall and the isotherms shift bodily downward in each case. The extrapolation of the linear section to zero concentration, as before, shows that the amount of phenol required to form a monolayer decreases to 0.42, 0.48 and 0.31 mg on outgassing at 600° and to 0.35, 0.39 and 0.31 mg on outgassing at 1000° in the case of the three carbon blacks respectively. This shows that as oxygen is gradually eliminated, the orientation of

the molecules in the adsorbed phase tends to change gradually from perpendicular to parallel position. The present investigation, thus highlights the influence of surface oxides in enhancing the adsorption of phenol from its solution in benzene and is also of interest in understanding oxygen status of carbons.

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